

NIST Assessment of Uncertainties for Standard Antenna Measurements

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Abstract: The National Institute of Standards and Technology calibrates electromagnetic compatibility reference antennas using the standard antenna method. This method uses a fundamental antenna to precisely measure the electric field. Frequencies of interest are 30 to 1000 MHz. Complete uncertainties are determined for calibrations performed on the open area test site and lead to a statement of uncertainty for the method. The results of this procedure yield a standard uncertainty of 0.4 dB.

INTRODUCTION

The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) calibrates antennas for testing electromagnetic compatibility (EMC). NIST uses the standard antenna method (SAM) to determine antenna factors [1]. This method relies on a fundamental antenna (a half-wave dipole) and a simplified converter (a diode) whose determination of a linearly polarized continuous-wave electric field (CW E-field) is easily calculable. This method is not directly dependent on the ground plane because the E-field at the test location is a result of the total electrical environment. This permits repeatable measurement of the E-field on the open area test site (OATS).

DESCRIPTION OF THE STANDARD ANTENNA METHOD

The standard antenna method uses a set of half-wave ($\lambda/2$) dipoles designed and built at NIST. The frequency range is 30 MHz to 1000 MHz.

The equations for determining the antenna factor of an antenna under test (AUT) using the SAM are:

$$E = V_{oc} / L_{eff} \quad (1a)$$

$$V_{oc} = M \cdot V_{dc} + B \quad (1b)$$

$$K_{AB} = E_{AB} - (V_{AB} + CL_{AB} + SA_{AB}) \quad (1c)$$

where

E = E-field strength, V/m,
 V_{oc} = open circuit rf voltage of NIST antenna, V,
 M = linear fit coefficient (slope),
 B = linear fit coefficient (Y intercept point), V,
 V_{dc} = dc voltage response of NIST antenna, V,
 L_{eff} = effective length of the NIST antenna, m,
 K_{AB} = antenna factor of antenna under test, dB,
 $E_{AB} = 20 \cdot \log(E)$, E-field strength, dB/m,
 V_{AB} = AUT response, dB,
 CL_{AB} = insertion loss in the cable, dB, and
 SA_{AB} = correction factor of the receiver, dB.

TEST SETUPS AND EQUIPMENT

The SAM consists of two parts, (1) the determination of the rf-to-dc voltage transfer function of the standard antenna performed inside the laboratory, and (2) the measurement of the E-field and the AUT's response on the OATS.

Figure 1. Block diagram of measurement setup for the rf-dc voltage transfer function.

Figure 1 shows the first measurement setup. The *rf source* consists of a rf signal generator and a low power (5 W) amplifier. The *rf power monitor* is a calibrated dual-directional coupler, coaxial cables, and power sensors. The *180° hybrid* and pair of customized coaxial t-connectors with 50 Ω loads provide a controlled rf signal to the NIST standard antenna's feed points. The dc voltage output from the standard antenna mount is measured using a *dc voltmeter* with a 100 M Ω input impedance.

The second part of the SAM is a measurement of the E-field and the AUT's response. The *rf source* and *rf*

power monitor blocks are as described earlier, but with a larger rf amplifier (80 W). The *transmitting antenna* is mounted on an adjustable tripod. The *E-field over ground screen* block symbolizes the interaction of the transmitted field with the environment of the OATS. The blocks for *standard antenna* and *antenna under test* represent the antennas used in the test. The *high-Z load* is a 100 MΩ resistance that is placed across the *dc voltmeter's* input. The *rf receiver* is a spectrum analyzer. All of the equipment, except for the antennas and cables, reside below the 30 m by 60 m ground plane in an underground room.

Figure 2. Block diagram of the standard antenna method on the OATS.

ASSESSMENT OF UNCERTAINTIES

Even though reference [1] details the standard antenna method at NIST, the description of the uncertainties of the measurement is cursory when compared to present requirements. With the current international emphasis on statements of uncertainty in EMC antenna measurements, a further look at uncertainties of the SAM is merited. A NIST document [2], that provides guidelines for uncertainty analysis, and several other publications [3 to 5], that offer procedures for EMC antenna measurements, provide a basis for our uncertainty analysis of the SAM. Further, in agreement with these publications, uncertainties will be expressed in decibels.

The individual uncertainties $u(x_i)$ in the SAM will be examined using equations (1a to 1c) and block diagrams (Figures 1 and 2):

- (1) rf-dc transfer function of the NIST antenna, u_{rf-dc}
- (2) effective length of the NIST antenna, u_{Leff}
- (3) dc voltage measurement, u_{dc}
- (4) rf voltage measurement, u_{rf}
- (5) loss in the receiving cable, u_{cbl}
- (6) rf source stability, u_{source}
- (7) alignment of antennas on OATS, u_{align}

- (8) E-field uniformity, u_{ufm}
- (9) measurement repeatability and E-field environmental interaction, $u_{rept.}$

A general formula can be applied for the propagation of independent uncertainties to obtain a combined standard uncertainty [2]. For a general linear function, the combined standard uncertainty is

$$u_c = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (u(x_i))^2} \quad (2)$$

We inspect each individual term $u(x_i)$ in the following sections to determine its effect on the combined standard uncertainty.

Calibration of Equipment

Calibration of instruments influence several uncertainty terms in the SAM. All of the instruments used in the SAM measurements are traceable to NIST standards, either calibrated by the manufacturer or traceable through internal calibration. Instruments used in the SAM are a power meter and sensor, a rf spectrum analyzer, a dc voltmeter, and a signal generator.

The Radio-Frequency Fields Group at NIST has a NIST type-IV power meter [6]. The worst-case uncertainty for this power sensor calibration is 0.5 % [7]. This type-IV power meter is used to calibrate the power sensors and the spectrum analyzer.

The amplified signal source depends upon the combined signal generator and the amplifier output. The power output of the signal generator is a relative value for the SAM and therefore only the resolution of the device is pertinent. The manufacturer's (mfr) rated resolution for the output power is 0.1 dB [8].

The power sensors were compared to the type-IV power meter. The 2 % repeatability of the power sensor measurements is combined with the 0.5 % of the type-IV calibration by using eq (2). This gives a standard uncertainty for the power sensors of

$$10 \cdot \log(1 + \sqrt{(0.02)^2 + (0.005)^2}) = 0.089 \text{ dB} \quad (3)$$

According to the manufacturer [9], the standard uncertainty of the DVM for dc voltage measurements is ≤ 0.01 percent. This converts to <0.001 dB.

The spectrum analyzer was calibrated with the type-IV power meter. Its average repeatability was 0.121 dB

(see 'RF voltage measurement of the AUT' section) giving a standard uncertainty with these measurements of $\sqrt{(0.121)^2 + (10 \cdot \log(1.005))^2} = 0.123$ dB. (4)

The standard uncertainties related to instrument calibration are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Standard Uncertainties for the Instruments of the SAM measurement.

Instrument	Uncertainty (dB)	Reference
signal generator	0.1	Mfr.
power sensors	0.089	Internal
dc voltmeter	<0.001	Mfr.
spectrum analyzer	0.123	Internal

RF-DC Transfer Function of the Standard Antenna

Since the response of the Shottky diode depends upon temperature, the voltage transfer function is measured at temperatures within 10 °C of the external environment. This variation caused a negligible difference in the results.

Standard antenna dc voltage measurements from 0.05 V to 2.5 V are referenced by means of figure 1. A linear fit is obtained for each set of data and this curve is then used to determine the open-circuit voltage from equation (1b). The correlation coefficient for the curve fit (r [2, p. 180]) is greater than 0.995. The set of curves for each standard antenna is analyzed for the maximum variation from curve to curve. Figure 3 shows a summary of the average and standard

Figure 3. Variation due to data curve fit, rf-dc voltage transfer measurement.

deviation of this variation expressed in decibels. A statistical study shows that there is an offset in the data around 0.04 dB and that most of the data have little variation. For dc voltages between 0.25 V and

1.50 V, which are typical, the average variation is 0.047 ± 0.012 dB.

Associated with this measurement, from figure 1, are thermocouple power sensors that have listed uncertainties of 0.089 dB, as reported in Table 1. The other items from figure 1, losses in the directional coupler and losses in the hybrid were also measured with a power sensor having uncertainties of 0.089 dB, for each component.

Combining these values as eq (2) suggests gives $U_{rf-dc} = [0.047^2 + 0.089^2 + 2 \cdot (0.089)^2]^{1/2}$, dB. (5)

Effective Length of the NIST Standard Antenna

Determination of the effective length L_{eff} of the NIST standard antenna was recently addressed [10]. Estimates of the change in the computed values of the effective length ∂L_{eff} were detailed for various measurement configurations. The uncertainty for this term is defined as $u_{L_{eff}} = 10 \cdot \log(1 + \partial L_{eff} / L_{eff})$. (6)

This data shows a normal distribution. Its statistical survey shows this uncertainty is reduced to an average value of $u_{L_{eff}} = 0.019 \pm 0.011$ dB. (7)

Figure 4. Average uncertainty of L_{eff} vs. frequency.

DC Voltage Measurement of the Standard Antenna

From Table 1, the uncertainty of the DVM is <0.001 dB. This value is below the round-off error for the uncertainty of the measurement. As expected, this is a very small value and will be considered negligible.

RF Voltage Measurement of the AUT

The response of the AUT is measured with a spectrum analyzer. The spectrum analyzer is compared to a calibrated power sensor for each reference level used.

Reference levels for the spectrum analyzer varied from +5 dBm to -20 dBm every 5 dB.

Figure 5 shows the repeatability of these comparison measurements. The average repeatability is 0.121 ± 0.035 dB. This data is normally distributed with some data trailing at the high end.

Figure 5. Repeatability of spectrum analyzer measurements over frequency.

The power sensor has an instrumentation uncertainty of 0.089 dB from Table 1. Combining these values as Equation (2) suggests gives

$$u_{rf} = [0.121^2 + 0.089^2]^{1/2} = 0.150 \text{ dB.} \quad (8)$$

Measurement of Loss in the Receiving Cable

The loss in the coaxial receiving cable was measured with a power sensor. The repeatability of these measurements is shown in Figure 6. The average repeatability is 0.029 ± 0.019 dB.

This part of the uncertainty has two components, the repeatability of the measurement and the calibration of the equipment. The total uncertainty of this term, including the instrument calibrations from Table 1, is

$$u_{cbi} = \sqrt{(0.029)^2 + (0.089)^2} = 0.094 \text{ dB.} \quad (9)$$

Figure 6. Repeatability of cable loss.

RF Source Stability

The rf source for SAM consists of a signal generator, an 80 W rf power amplifier, and a set of low-pass filters. The signal generator by itself has a very stable and repeatable rf output. The rf amplifier's output depends upon its warm-up time and the level of rf power into the unit. For this type of measurement, the amplifier is allowed to stabilize for 20 min and the input rf power is on only long enough to take a steady reading. A reading is considered steady when the rf power monitor's reading is stable for a few seconds. Since the amplitude drift in the amplifier can be compensated with the output of the signal generator; this leaves only the resolution of the signal generator as a component for uncertainty. Therefore, from Table 1, the uncertainty due to this component is $u_{source} = 0.1$ dB.

Alignment of Antennas on OATS

The transmitting and receiving antennas are placed on tripods or on an antenna mast for measurement on the OATS. Position alignment includes the setting of height for each antenna and the separation between antennas as well as the orientation of each antenna. The position and orientation of an antenna on a tripod is repeatable within 1 cm in each direction (height and separation). The antenna mast has a motor-controlled pulley system that is also repeatable within 1 cm in each direction. These positioning variations project changes in the E-field of $u_{align} = 0.08$ dB for two dipole antennas with a typical separation of 10 m and antenna heights of 2 m.

E-field Uniformity

The characteristics of both receiving and transmitting antennas affect the geometry of the E-field and are directly relevant to the combined standard uncertainty. Included in this term is each antenna's directivity, its height above the ground plane, radiation pattern, and physical size. The directivity of the AUT will depend in part upon its environment; this term will be included in the resultant antenna factor. An increase in the alignment uncertainty due to variations in the directivity is estimated to be 0.1 dB. The radiation pattern is of concern when it differs from the standard dipole pattern, since the standard dipole is the reference antenna. Estimated uncertainties on the order of 0.15 dB can be expected. The size of the antenna dictates the spatial volume used for measurement of

the E-field. So a larger antenna requires an E-field that is uniform over a larger volume than is required for a small antenna. This adds another 0.15 dB of uncertainty due to the expected uniformity of the E-field over different volumes for typical EMC antennas. Combining these as described earlier using equation (2) gives

$$u_{ufm} = \sqrt{(0.10)^2 + (0.15)^2 + (0.15)^2} = 0.235 \text{ dB.} \quad (10)$$

Measurement Repeatability and E-field Environmental Interaction

This value is the most difficult value to assess. It depends on the interaction of the transmitted E-field with the environment of the OATS. This environment includes intrusive time-varying ambient signals, reflection from nearby objects, and nonideal reflection off the ground plane. All interactions are, of course, frequency dependent.

Complexities are also inherent with the instrumentation. Ambient signals can be viewed only when the measurement signal is turned off. Narrow-band filters in the receiver improve selectivity and reject most of the unwanted or non-measurement signals. The diode detector on the standard antenna's response allows for a broadband response to be measured with the dc voltmeter.

At NIST, ambient signals are required to be less than or equal to 10 % of the test signal, as measured with the standard antenna. Higher signal strength from the source results in an ambient signal overwhelmed by the test signal. Sometimes, this is not effective for large ambient signals at certain times and requires a change in the orientation of the antennas to minimize detection of the intrusive E-field. This extreme measure is necessary only at a few frequencies and is rarely needed.

Repeatability of measurements and use of check standard comparisons are standard components of SAM tests at NIST. AUTs are measured at least two independent times and the results compared. The check standard antennas are a set of broadband dipoles that are measured with every AUT. Results are compared to historical data to ensure measurement repeatability at the site.

Repeatability of SAM tests at NIST is ≤ 0.25 dB for any AUT. Check standard antenna repeatability is also ≤ 0.25 dB, based on historical data. If we assume

rectangular distribution for data repeatability, the resulting standard uncertainty is

$$u_{rept} = 0.25 / \sqrt{3} = 0.144 \text{ dB.} \quad (11)$$

SUMMARY OF UNCERTAINTIES

The individual standard uncertainties for this method are detailed in Section 4 and summarized in Table 2. Uncertainties are classified into type A and type B [2]. Combining the terms in Table 2 by using equation (2) gives the combined standard uncertainty,

$$u_c = 0.4 \text{ dB.} \quad (12)$$

To obtain the expanded uncertainty U , we use a coverage factor of $k = 2$ [2], giving $U = 0.8$ dB. (13)

Table 2. Standard antenna individual uncertainties.

Description	Term	Type	Value (dB)
rf-to-dc transfer function of the standard antenna	u_{rf-dc}	A	0.161
effective length of the standard antenna	u_{Leff}	A	0.019
dc voltage measurement of the standard antenna	u_{dc}	B	neg.
rf voltage measurement of the AUT	u_{rf}	A	0.150
measurement of loss in the receiving cable	u_{cbl}	A	0.094
rf source stability	u_{source}	B	0.10
alignment of antennas on OATS	u_{align}	B	0.08
E-field uniformity	U_{ufm}	B	0.235
Measurement repeatability and E-field environmental interaction	U_{rept}	A	0.144

CONCLUSIONS

Most of the antenna calibration work for the EMC measurement industry at NIST has been with biconical, log-periodic, and tuned-dipole antennas. The antenna factor at frequencies between 30 MHz and 1000 MHz is measured using the standard antenna method, which includes an uncertainty analysis needed for meaningful measurement results.

When uncertainties are assessed, the full sequence of measurements needs to be addressed and not just individual segments. This paper accurately presents

the uncertainties for SAM measurements on the OATS. The largest individual uncertainty is in determining the antenna characteristics. This uncertainty will be present for any type of measurement procedure. The next two largest individual uncertainties are with the E-field transfer function of the standard antenna and the rf voltage measurement of the AUT. These three terms need to be reduced for any substantial reduction in the expanded uncertainty. These three terms will be further analyzed in future work.

Current guidelines for uncertainty analysis have been applied for determining antenna factor of an AUT at NIST. The result of this analysis yields a standard uncertainty of 0.4 dB.

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